

RNR74802 (Sona/ Manoharsali) has long slender grains and RNR1535 (Tella Hamsa/ARC14302) has medium bold grains. They are now in minikit trials in A.P. □

Table 2. Average ShB scores, 1986 and 1987.

Cultivar	Disease score
RNR6250	4.3
RNR74802	4.5
RNR1535	4.8
RNR1-138-8-1	5.0
RNR1806	5.1
RNR18953	5.1
RNR98357	5.4
RNR9075	5.4
RNR133-87	5.4
RNR10244	5.5
RNR89128	5.6
RNR286	5.6
RNR3070	5.7
RNR9062	5.8
RNR99372	5.9
RNR1-111-63	5.9
RNR82096	6.0
RNR5 204	6.0
RNR15-97-36	6.0
RNR52147	6.1
RNR32341	6.1
RNR6827	6.2
RNR16210	6.5
RNR99514	6.6
RNR17085	6.7
RNR9139	6.8
RNR15-84-11	6.8
RNR769	6.8
RNR18586	6.8
RNR99378	6.8
RNR10212	6.9
RNR10208	6.9
RNR99180	7.1
RNR18545	7.1
RNR17-1864	7.1
RNR18864	7.1
RNR527	7.1
RNR16050	7.2
TN1 (check)	7.2
SE (m) ±	0.4

Field evaluation for resistance to rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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Severe yellowing and stunting affected rice in the Kuttanad area of Kerala, India, during 1988 kharif (Aug-Sep to Oct-Nov). Serological tests at the

Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, confirmed the presence of GSV strain 2 (GSV-2).

We screened 7 varieties, 8 prerelease cultivars from 3 crosses, and 70 promising cultivars from 16 crosses for resistance to GSV-2 in the field.

None of the seven varieties showed resistance (see table). Of the eight prerelease cultivars, only KAU168

(ARC6650/ Jaya) showed moderate resistance.

Twelve cultivars from the crosses MO 5/ Improved Sona, MO 4/ Culture 25331, Culture 1954/ Jyothi, Jyothi/ Culture 25331, Vykatharyan/ MO 6, Thonnooran/ IR8, and Thonnooran/ MO 6 showed moderate resistance. □

Varietal resistance to GSV strain 2. Kerala, India, 1988 kharif.

Variety or culture	Parentage	GSV-2 damage ^a (0-9)	Grain yield (t/ha)
MO 4 (Bhadra)		5	0.2
MO 5 (Asha (R))		5	1.0
MO 6 (Pavizham)		4	2.3
MO 7 (Karthika)		4	1.3
Jyothi		4	1.4
Mahaveera		4	0.9
Jaya		4	0.8
KAU93	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.1
KAU126	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.8
KAU129	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.6
KAU153-1	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	1.4
KAU168	ARC6650/Jaya	2	4.4
KAU170	ARC6650/Jaya	4	1.8
KAU200	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	2.0
KAU204	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	1.3
M28-1-1	MO 5/Improved Sona	3	1.4
M38-2-1-1	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	2.1
M38-2-1-2	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	1.3
M38-4-1	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	1.9
M38-8-2	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	3.1
M39-3-1	Culture 1954/Jyothi	3	1.7
M40-5-2	Jyothi/Culture 25331	3	1.5
M41-16-2	Vykatharyan/ MO 6	3	2.1
M48-11-1	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	1.4
M48-11-2	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	1.9
M48-11-3	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	2.9
M49-2-3	Thonnooran/ MO 6	3	1.6

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Resistance of TKM6 and IR20 to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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In the greenhouse, TKM6 and IR lines with TKM6 in their parentage show high levels of resistance to RTSV infection, but are susceptible to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) infection. Field trials at the IRRI farm confirm the resistance of TKM6 and IR20 to RTSV.

In 1987 wet season (WS), TKM6 and TN1 planted in 25- × 50-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing were subjected to natural infection. Leaf samples were collected at 18, 32, 49, and 92 d after transplanting (DT) from a sample of 36 hills. Each plot had 10 sampling units arranged in a W-pattern.

In 1988 WS, IR20 (IR262-24-3/TKM6) was planted in 21- × 21-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Leaf samples were collected from a sample of 9 hills at 14, 28, 42, and 55 DT. The 46 sampling units/plot were arranged in a quincuncial pattern. Leaf samples were

RTBV and RTSV incidence on TKM6 and TN1 at different days after transplanting. IRRRI, 1987 WS.

indexed by ELISA for the presence of RTBV and RTSV.

In 1987, at 92 DT (when TN1 had 100% infection with both RTBV and RTSV), TKM6 had 69% infection with RTBV only (see figure). In the 1988 trial, when tungro incidence was relatively lower, RTBV incidence on

IR20 was 0.6% at 14 DT and increased to 2.6% at 55 DT. Very low infection with both RTBV and RTSV and no infection with RTSV alone were recorded.

Infectivity test of green leafhopper (GLH) collected at 44 DT from IR20 plots yielded a low percentage of

Infectivity on TN1 seedlings of GLH collected 44 DT from field plots planted to IR20 and TN1. IRRRI, 1988 WS.

Source of GLH	GLH tested (no.)	GLH transmitted (%)		
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR20	129	0.01	0.01	0
TN1	132	42	13	2

infective leafhoppers; GLH collected from an adjacent field planted to TN1 with 30% tungro incidence had high infectivity (see table).

Because transmission of RTBV by GLH depends on the presence of RTSV, RTBV incidence will not increase remarkably nor become RTBV + RTSV if the population of RTSV-infected or RTBV + RTSV-infected plants is very low. □

Bacterial blight (BB) resistance in some Nepal rice cultivars

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We evaluated nine traditional and two improved rices reported resistant to BB in Nepal in the greenhouse at IRRRI

against Philippine races of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Plants were clip-inoculated at maximum tillering with inoculum (10^8 CFU/ml) from each race group. Lesion development was measured on 10 randomly inoculated leaves of each cultivar 14 d after inoculation.

Reaction to the races varied significantly among cultivars (see table).

Rato anadi was highly resistant to races 2 and 5, Saeto anadi was resistant only to race 5. Laxmi was moderately resistant to races 1, 4, and 5. In general, the Nepalese rices had low levels of resistance to the Philippine races of *X. c* pv. *oryzae*. □

Reaction of some Nepalese rice cultivars to 6 Philippine races of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. IRRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Lesion length ^a (cm)						Mean
	1 (PXO61)	2 (PXO86)	3 (PXO79)	4 (PXO71)	5 (PXO112)	6 (PXO99)	
Ghaiya	5.14 c	10.40 bc	7.21 c	19.41 b	6.42 c	35.65 a	14.04 bc
Saeto anadi	27.48 a	26.54 ab	16.70 b	23.57 ab	1.35 c	25.21 ab	20.14 a
Rato anadi	18.06 bc	1.24 d	12.61 c	23.03 ab	1.08 d	28.87 a	14.15 bc
Choto marshi	21.89 a-c	11.87 c	12.91 bc	22.93 ab	17.56 bc	30.15 a	19.55 a
Ramdulari	18.68 b	20.88 ab	12.99 b	18.90 b	14.11 b	30.45 a	19.34 a
Malbhog	12.27 b	9.04 b	8.89 b	10.79 b	12.70 b	28.68 a	13.73 bc
Gadar	12.69 bc	22.42 a	8.74 c	8.48 c	21.67 b	32.93 a	17.82 ab
Sataraj	14.63 ab	11.67 ab	7.40 b	18.17 a	14.77 ab	18.55 a	14.20 bc
Jaswa	16.31 bc	25.18 ab	16.51 bc	13.67 c	13.25 c	28.95 a	18.98 a
Janaki ^b	10.07 b	20.72 a	8.66 b	8.76 b	5.53 b	11.84 ab	10.93 c
Laxmi ^b	4.86 b	18.13 a	9.94 ab	6.62 b	4.10 b	17.62 a	10.21 c
TN1	22.56 b	21.24 b	17.02 b	23.91 ab	7.04 c	32.89 a	20.78 a
Mean	15.39 bc	16.61 b	11.63 cd	16.52 b	9.96 d	26.81 a	16.15

^aDisease was assessed by lesion length: 0.0-3.0 cm = resistant, 3.1-7 cm = moderately resistant, 7.1-10.0 cm = moderately susceptible, 10.1 cm or longer = susceptible. In a row, means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bImproved cultivar.

Insect resistance

Screening rice varieties for damage caused by *Oebalus insularis* (Stål)

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In 1985, insect pests and diseases affected about 50% of the rice area in Cuba. The pests that caused the greatest damage were water weevil and stink bug. *O. insularis* is the most plentiful and widespread bug species. Use of resistant varieties plays an important role in widely accepted integrated control.